

Supporting Information: Information requirements under the essential-use concept: PFAS case studies

Juliane Glüge, Rachel London, Ian T. Cousins, Jamie DeWitt, Gretta Goldenman, Dorte Herzke, Rainer Lohmann, Mark Miller, Carla A. Ng, Sharyle Patton, Xenia Trier, Zhanyun Wang, Martin Scheringer*

* corresponding author: scheringer@usys.ethz.ch

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1) Data collected for substances in the alternatives assessment

The data collected from the Classification & Labelling (C&L) Inventory, the ECHA REACH registration database, and data generated with EPI Suite are listed in the accompanying MS Excel document "Gluege_et_al_SI-2.xlsx" (SI-2), separated according to the case studies.

2) Additional information on the case studies

2.1) Bicycle lubricants

Fluoroadditive powders are a class of fluoropolymers primarily based on PTFE.¹ They are of small particle size and relatively low molecular weight. It has been stated that fluoroadditive powders are also used in lubricants¹ and probably also in bike chain lubricants. Apparently, fluoroadditive powders enhance the abrasion resistance, reduce the coefficient of friction and mechanical wear and that they reduce surface contamination.²

The use of PTFE in lubricants (including lubricants for cars) is one of the major uses of fluoropolymers in the Nordic Countries. Of the 13,800 t of PFAS polymers that have been used in between 2000 and 2017 in Sweden, Finland, Norway and Denmark, 1450 t were used in lubricants.^{3,4}

2.2) Carpets

A recent publication estimated the stock of PFAS in California carpets. For 2017, it was estimated that the total amount of PFAS in in-use carpets is ~60 tonnes.⁵

Some information on chemical synthesis processes and ingredients of carpets can be found in patents, for example in patent US005889138A⁶ and patent US005889138A⁷. The first one describes a process for making stain-resistant nylon fibers from highly sulfonated nylon copolymers and discloses the use of 1,3-benzenedicarboxylic acid, 5-sulfo-, lithium salt (1:1), polymer with 1,6-hexanediamine and hexanedioic acid (CAS no. 222173-52-6). The latter one is a method for continuous production of stain-resistant nylon using 1,3-benzenedicarboxylic acid, 5-sulfo-, polymer with hexahydro-2H-azepin-2-one and 1,6-hexanediamine (CAS no. 31227-03-9). However, no information is available on these two substances in the public domain.

2.3) Cleaning products

Based on data from the SPIN Database, the use of PFAS in cleaning products accounted for 21 out of 20,160 t of PFAS used in Sweden, Finland, Norway and Denmark in between 2000 to 2017.

2.3.1) Floor polish

Non-fluorinated alternatives have been developed for floor polish. Patent CN101293999⁸ from 3M describes, e.g., the use of a fluorine-free wetting agent comprising an organosilicon and an alkyne diol-based polyether or a fatty oil-alkene oxide copolymer. According to SciFinderⁿ, the alkyne diol-based polyether is poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl), α -hydro- ω -hydroxy-, ether with tetramethyldecynediol (2:1) (CAS no 175801-05-5). An alternative assessment of this polymer was not possible because there were no data in the C&L inventory and no REACH registration. Evonik advertises its Dynol 607 (poly(oxy-1,2-ethanediyl), α , α' -[1,4-dimethyl-1,4-bis(3-methylbutyl)-2-butyne-1,4-diyl]bis[ω -hydroxy-, (9CI, ACl)] CAS no. 169117-72-0 as surfactant for floor polish.⁹ According to the C&L inventory, this compound is harmful to aquatic life with long-lasting effects (see SI-2) and therefore not an ideal alternative.

2.3.2) Carpet spot cleaner and aftermarket carpet-care products

PFAS-free carpet-spot cleaner are available on the market. One example is the Stain + Odoer Remover from ECOS.¹⁰ It is stated that a plant derived surfactant, caprylyl/myristyl glucoside (CAS no.

68515-73-1 and 110615-47-9) is used.¹⁰ According to its REACH registration dossier, caprylyl/myristyl glucoside is neither persistent nor bioaccumulative. However, the C&L inventory has a notification that this compound is harmful to aquatic life with long-lasting effects (see SI-2).

Alternatives exist also to PFAS in aftermarket carpet-care products. Non-PFAS chemical solutions on the market include silicone dioxide in nanoparticle form¹¹ and proprietary anionic non-fluorinated polymers.^{12,13}

2.4) Additional case study: climbing ropes

Uses: PFAS, probably C6 side-chain fluorinated polymers, are used in climbing ropes to protect the ropes from water and dirt.

Availability of alternatives: The rope producer Edelrid introduced in 2018 a hydrophobic coating for climbing ropes that is PFAS free.¹⁴ Ropes with this coating meet the water-repellency standard of the International Climbing and Mountaineering Federation and absorb only 1–2% of their own weight in water.

Alternative assessment: The composition of the PFAS-free coating is confidential business information, so no assessment of alternatives is possible. The rope producer themselves have not performed a hazard or risk assessment, but rely on the chemical safety data sheet provided by the chemical manufacturer of the waterproofing chemical for chemical hazard information (Edelrid, personal communication).

Conclusion: Technically, PFAS are not needed in climbing ropes and an alternative is on the market so that this use of PFAS is non-essential. However, an assessment of alternatives was not possible because no information on the composition and properties of the alternative was made available.

2.5) Chrome plating

As a general note, chromium (VI) was assessed as chromium trioxide and chromium (III) as chromium chloride as described in the authorisation process for chromium trioxide use.¹⁵

There are basically two processes in which chromium (VI) is used for the plating on plastics: in the etching of plastic (pre-treatment process) and for applying a metallic chrome coating on top of the plastic substrate (electroplating). In the alternative assessment of Gerhardt Kunststofftechnik it is pointed out that both steps are interlinked and cannot be seen as standalone processes. They also state that without an adequate pre-treatment, the high-quality of the final product cannot be reached.¹⁶

2.5.1) Pre-treatment (etching) process

PFAS are used as effective wetting agents in the etching pre-treatment process. Hauser et al. (2020)¹⁷ stated that if chromium (VI) and thus also the fluorosurfactants are to be dispensed with, substitution is possible by a two-stage process. The first step would involve swelling (e.g. with ethylene and butyl diglycol), the second step oxidation (e.g. with potassium permanganate). An optional third step could be neutralization.¹⁷

In their alternative assessment, Gerhardt Kunststofftechnik concluded that as of 2016, “permanganate based alternatives for etching of plastic substrates is not technically feasible. From a

Table S1: Major biosurfactant classes for MEOR, adapted from Varjani (2017) and Desai and Banat (1997). Not for all biosurfactants listed chemical structures are provided.

Biosurfactant	Example
<u>Glycolipids</u>	
Rhamnolipids (e.g. CAS no. 4348-76-9)	<p>Absolute stereochemistry shown.</p>
Trehalolipids	
Sophorolipids (e.g. CAS no. 117854-19-0)	<p>Absolute stereochemistry shown.</p>
Cellbiolipids	
<u>Lipoproteins or Lipopeptides</u>	
Iturin (e.g. CAS no. 64667-10-3)	<p>Absolute stereochemistry shown.</p>

Surfactin
(e.g. CAS no. 24730-31-2)

Viscosin
(e.g. CAS no. 27127-62-4)

Lichenysin
Peptide-lipid
Serrawettin
(e.g. CAS no. 5285-25-6)

Subtilisin

Phospholipids, fatty acids or natural lipids

Surface-active antibiotics

Gramicidin

Polymixin

Fatty acids or natural lipids

Polymeric biosurfactants

Emulsan

Alasan

Liposan

(e.g. CAS 1077-28-7)

Biodispersan

Mannan-lipid protein

Carbohydrate-protein-lipid

Particulate biosurfactants

Vesicles and fimbria

Whole cells

2.7) Processing aids for aqueous emulsion polymerization of fluoropolymers

2.7.1) General notes

Fluoropolymers can be produced by several methods, including suspension polymerization (e.g. patents DE2416452,²² DE3135598,²³ and EP649863²⁴); aqueous emulsion polymerization (e.g. patents DE2052495,²⁵ and DE2639109²⁶); solution polymerization (e.g. patents DE2019150,²⁷ US4535136,²⁸ US5663255²⁹); polymerization using supercritical CO (e.g. patents JP4601103³⁰ and EP964009³¹); and polymerization in the gas phase (e.g. patent US4861845³²).

2.7.2) Fluorine-free processing aids for the polymerization of vinylidene fluoride (VDF) patented by Arkema

Arkema has developed a whole toolbox of methods and emulsifiers to produce PVDF without fluorosurfactants. Table S2 and Table S3 show fluorine-free emulsifiers patented by Arkema in between 2004 to 2020. One set of substances are emulsifiers containing blocks of polyethylene glycol (PEG), polypropylene glycol (PPG) and/or polytetramethylene glycol (PTMG) (Table S2). They are included inter alia in the patents US20060281845,³³ US20070135546,³⁴ US20070082993,³⁵ US20120142858,³⁶ and WO2020101963.³⁷ Beside the Chemical Abstract Service (CAS) numbers, Table S2 also contains a short summary on their alternative assessment (AA). More details on the AA can be found in the accompanying excel spread sheet (Gluege_et_al_SI-2.xlsx).

Table S2: Emulsifiers containing blocks of PEG, PPG and/or PTMG that are included in patents US20060281845,³³ US20070135546,³⁴ US20070082993,³⁵ US20120142858,³⁶ and WO2020101963.³⁷

Substance name	CAS No.	Summary of AA	Ref
Polyethylene glycol (PEG)	25322-68-3	reduced hazard	33-37
Polyethylene glycol acrylate (PEGA)	60182-11-8	no information	33
Polyethylene glycol monoacrylate	26403-58-7	no C&L notifications	34-37
Polyethylene glycol monomethacrylate	25736-86-1	reduced hazard	37
Polyethylene glycol methacrylate (PEG-MA)	9056-77-3	no information	35
Polyethylene glycol monobutyl ether (PEGBE)	9004-77-7	reduced hazard	34,35,37

Polyethylene glycol phenol oxide (Triton X-100)	9002-93-1	endocrine disrupting	33-35,37
Polyethylene glycol dimethyl ether	24991-55-7	CLP Reproductive toxicant 2	37
Polypropylene glycol (PPG)	25322-69-4	reduced hazard	33-37
Polypropylene glycol acrylate (PPGA)	58856-72-7	no information	33-35,37
Polypropylene glycol monoacrylate	50858-51-0	CLP Aquatic Chronic 2	36
Poly(propylene glycol) methacrylate (PPG-MA)	62851-97-2	no information	34-37
Polypropylene glycol dimethacrylate	25852-49-7	no C&L notifications	34-36
Polytetramethylene glycol (PTMG)	25190-06-1	no information	34-37

Additional patents from Arkema describe the use of alkyl phosphonate surfactants (US20070032591³⁸), vinyl/acrylic acids or a salt thereof (WO2012030784³⁹), polyvinyl/acrylic acid or a salt thereof (WO2007018783⁴⁰), alkanesulfonates (US20050239983⁴¹), siloxane surfactant (EP1462461⁴²), and 3-allyloxy-2-hydroxy-1-propane sulfonic acid salts as surfactants (EP1475395⁴³). According to information provided by Arkema in a personal communication, the emulsifier used in a process is selected on the basis of the desired properties of the PVDF polymer.

Table S3: Additional fluorine-free emulsifier for the polymerization of PVDF patented by Arkema. The patents are US20070032591,³⁸ WO2012030784,³⁹ WO2007018783,⁴⁰ US20050239983,⁴¹ EP1462461,⁴² and EP1475395.⁴³

Substance name	CAS No.	Summary of AA	Ref
Dodecylphosphonic acid	5137-70-2	Reduced hazard	38
Sodium vinylsulfonate	3039-83-6	CLP Aquatic Chronic 3	39
Vinylphosphonic acid	1746-03-8	Reduced hazard	39
Vinylsulfonic acid	1184-84-5	Reduced hazard	39
Itaconic acid	97-65-4	CLP Aquatic Acute 1, CLP Aquatic Chronic 1	39
Methacrylic acid	79-41-4	Reduced hazard	39
Acrylic acid	79-10-7	CLP Aquatic Acute 1	39
Poly(vinylphosphonic acid)	27754-99-0	Reduced hazard	40
Poly(vinylsulfonic acid)	26101-52-0	No information	40
Poly(methacrylic acid)	25087-26-7	Reduced hazard	40
Poly(acrylic acid)	9003-01-4	CLP Carcinogen category 1A, CLP Mutagen category 1B	40
Sodium 1-octanesulfonate monohydrate	207596-29-0	Reduced hazard	41
1,2-Octanedisulfonic acid, sodium salt (1:2)	139473-92-0	No information	41
Sodium decanesulfonate	13419-61-9	Reduced hazard	41
Sodium octanesulfonate	5324-84-5	Reduced hazard	41
Dimethylsilanediol-ethylene oxide block copolymer	156309-06-7	No information	42
Polyethylene glycol monomethyl ether	27306-78-1	CLP Aquatic Chronic 2,	42

mono[3-[methylbis(trimethylsiloxy)silyl]propyl] ether		CLP Aquatic Chronic 3	
Poly(dimethylsiloxane)	9016-00-6	CLP Aquatic Chronic 4	42
1-Propanesulfonic acid, 2-hydroxy-3-(2-propen-1-yloxy)-, ammonium salt (1:1)	101324-88-3	No information	43
1-Propanesulfonic acid, 2-hydroxy-3-(2-propen-1-yloxy)-, sodium salt (1:1)	52556-42-0	Very persistent; CLP Reproductive toxicant 2	43
Dimethylsilanediol-ethylene oxide block copolymer*	156309-06-7	No information	43
Dimethylsilanediol-ethylene oxide-propylene oxide block copolymer*	156309-05-6	No information	43
Ethylene oxide-propylene oxide block copolymer*	106392-12-5	Reduced hazard	43
Polyethylene glycol*			
1,1,1,3,3,5,5-Heptamethyltrisiloxane*	2895-07-0	Reduced hazard	43
1,1,1,3,5,5,5-Heptamethyltrisiloxane*	1873-88-7	Very Persistent, very bioaccumulative	43
Betaine*	107-43-7	Reduced hazard	43

* (possible/optional cosurfactant in ref. 43)

2.7.3) Fluorine-free processing aids for the polymerization of VDF by other manufacturer than Arkema

Other manufacturers of fluoropolymers beside Arkema have also patented fluorine-free processing aids for the polymerization of VDF. It is not known if these processes are used in practice. Du Pont has developed a process that uses allylphosphate esters (US20080262177⁴⁴) and another process that uses hydrocarbon anionic surfactants (US20080125558⁴⁵) for the polymerization of VDF. 3M has developed at least two processes, one with carbosilane surfactants (US7678859⁴⁶) and one with derivatives of sugar (polyol compounds) (WO2011014715⁴⁷).

2.7.4) Processing aids for the polymerization of fluoropolymers in general

Patent US20120116003⁴⁸ describes a process where fluorosurfactants are greatly reduced in the aqueous emulsion polymerization of fluoromonomers to form e.g. non-melt-processible perfluoroplastics such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and melt-fabricable perfluoroplastics such as tetrafluoroethylene/hexafluoropropylene copolymer (FEP) and tetrafluoroethylene/perfluoro(alkyl vinyl ether) (PFA).

The patents also show the development and improvement of fluorine-free emulsifiers. It was stated in a patent from 2007 (US20070015865⁴⁹) that although emulsifier-free polymerization processes are known, the presence of fluorinated surfactants is still desirable because "it can yield stable fluoropolymer particle dispersions in high yield and in a more environmental friendly way than for example polymerizations conducted in an organic solvent". However, the newly developed processes, e.g. patent US20120116003⁴⁸ yield solid contents of > 45% wt and use an aqueous medium. It was stated in another patent (WO2013169571⁵⁰) that fluoropolymer resins polymerized with hydrocarbon surfactants are prone to thermally induced discoloration, which is unwanted.

However, patents WO2013169571⁵⁰ and WO2013169581⁵¹ describe processes for reducing thermally induced discoloration that seem to solve the problem.

There are also other recent patents that disclose methods for manufacturing fluoropolymer using fluorine-free surfactants. Examples are the patents WO2018181898⁵², WO2018181904⁵³, WO2019172382⁵⁴, and WO2020136679⁵⁵ from 3M.

2.8. Semiconductor industry

Beside the use of PFAS as photoacid generator in the photoresist, PFAS can also be part of the photoresist itself, act as a photosensitizer or quencher in the photoresist.⁴ PFAS may also be used to add a thin coating to the photoresist to reduce reflections.⁵⁶ Additionally, PFAS may be used as surfactants in the developers, as etching agents or in ancillary products such as edge bead removers.⁵⁶ PFAS are also used in rinsing and cleaning solutions for wafers, and in working fluids for vacuum pumps and highly inert molds and pipes. Additional uses of PFAS in the semiconductor industry are described by Glüge et al. (2020).⁴

2.8.1) Photoacid generators

Some fluorine-free photoacid generators (PAGs) are described in patents. For example, aromatic PAGs in patent WO2009091704⁵⁷ and heteroaromatic PAGs in patents WO2009091702⁵⁸ and US20110183259.⁵⁹ The latter patent is currently active (owned by Global Foundries Inc.) and includes, among others, the PAG triphenylsulfonium benzo[b]thiophene-2-sulfonic acid, 4(or 7)-nitro-, ion(1-) (TPS TBNO).

2.8.2) Immersion liquid, developer solution and rinse solution

The identity of the fluorine-free alternative used in the BASF patent is vague. In patent WO2012127342⁶⁰ the identity is described as:

“[0040] Preferably, the potentially anionic and anionic groups of the fluorine-free anionic surfactants A are selected from the group consisting of carboxylic acid, sulfonic acid, phosphonic acid, sulfuric acid monoester, phosphoric acid monoester and phosphoric acid diester groups and carboxylate, sulfonate, phosphonates, monoester sulfate, monoester phosphate and diester phosphate groups.

[0041] Preferably, the counterions of the anionic groups are selected from the group consisting of ammonium, lithium, sodium, potassium and magnesium cations. Most preferably, ammonium is used as the counterion.

....

[0045] Preferably, the fluorine-free amphoteric surfactant A is selected from the group consisting of alkylamine oxides, in particular alkyldimethylamine oxides; acyl-/dialkylethylenediamines, in particular sodium acylamphoacetate, disodium acylamphodipropionate, disodium alkylamphodiacetate, sodium acylamphohydroxypropylsulfonate, disodium acylamphodiacetate, sodium acylamphopropionate, and *N*-coconut fatty acid amidoethyl-*N*-hydroxyethylglycinate sodium salts; *N*-alkylamino acids, in particular aminopropyl alkylglutamide, alkylaminopropionic acid, sodium imidodipropionate and lauroamphocarboxyglycinate”

3) Manufacturers contacted

Table S4: List of manufacturers contacted. All manufacturers included here provided provided information on the respective case studies, some of them also reviewed the case-study descriptions and provided feedback.

PFAS use	Manufacturer contacted	Date of contact	Review of case study description
Bicycle lubricants	Green Oil	August 2021	No
Bicycle lubricants	Fenwick's Bike	August 2021	Partial
Carpets	Aquafil	April 2021	No
Carpets	RAL Environment	June 2019	No
Carpets	Nordic Ecolabel	June 2019	No
Climbing ropes	Edelrid	March 2021	Yes
Chrome plating	Faraday Technology	May 2019, May and August 2021	Yes, extensive
Chrome plating	Atotech	May 2019 and May 2021	No
Chrome plating	MacDermid Enthone Industrial Solutions	June and August 2021	Yes, extensive
Processing aids for emulsion polymerization of fluoropolymers	Arkema	August 2021	Yes, extensive
Semiconductor Industry (PAGs)	IBM	August 2021	Yes, extensive

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